

Pharmacological and Toxicological Effects of Chemotherapy on Cancer Patients in This Era and The Role of Open Access Journals in This Matter

Editorial

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Chemotherapy Background

Chemotherapy was developed and used since the World War I from the chemical weapon program of the United State of America (USA). Since then chemotherapy has become as one of the most important and significant treatment of cancer. Its main mechanism of action is by destroying the cancer cells which are characterized by their high multiplication and growth speed [1,2]. However when comparing chemotherapy with other types of treatments, it still remain potentially high risk with many side effects which are difficult to manage. Chemotherapy used required the involvement of various clinical professionals during its various stages of

administration and enormous patient health care is needed to overcome its side effects [1,3].

Open Access Journal Role in This Matter

Open access journals specifically (International Journal of Clinical Pharmacology & Toxicology) will play a very important role in developing exchange and sharing of experience between clinical staff and this will mainly leads to knowledge grows up. And this is the main objective for each research conducted in the medical field [4]. Therefore open access journals role consider very important specifically in this point.

Conclusion

Open access journal consider as a constructive way in exchange the knowledge related with chemotherapy pharmacological and toxicological effect in cancer treatment. Therefore, Open Access Journals play as a very supportive role in this matter i.e., by increasing knowledge exchange.

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